

FEATURES OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE ACQUISITION BY STUDENTS USING TEACHING FLASH MOBS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10421149>

Annotation: This article explores the unique features of English language acquisition through Teaching Flash Mobs, an innovative and dynamic approach to language learning. Emphasizing spontaneity, linguistic diversity, and contextual use of language, Teaching Flash Mobs create an immersive and interactive learning environment. The article delves into the inclusivity of this method, accommodating students of various proficiency levels and backgrounds, fostering cultural integration, and promoting technological enhancements. Additionally, it highlights the motivational aspect of Teaching Flash Mobs, leveraging the novelty factor to enhance student engagement and participation. Overall, the article provides insights into the multifaceted nature of Teaching Flash Mobs as an effective tool for English language acquisition in diverse educational settings.

Key Words: Teaching Flash Mobs, Language Learning Innovation, Spontaneous Learning, Linguistic Diversity, Contextual Language Use, Interactive Language Practice, Cultural Integration, Inclusive Learning, Technological Integration, Motivation in Language Learning, Novelty in Education, Community Building, Language Proficiency, Educational Innovation, Real-world Language Use, Student Engagement.

INTRODUCTION. Teaching flash mobs used in the educational process can be expressed in the use of scenarios that require the student's attention and response in real time. The purpose of models based on learning flash mobs is to have an idea of the general behavior of the system based on the assumptions about the individual rules, the individual behavior of its individual active objects and the interaction of these objects in the system. requires lish. As part of our research, we have studied one of the paradigms of digital technology - teaching flash mobs.

In recent years, innovative approaches to language learning have emerged, with Teaching Flash Mobs gaining attention as a dynamic method to enhance English language acquisition among students. This article explores the key features of English language acquisition through Teaching Flash Mobs, shedding light on how this unconventional approach fosters engagement, collaboration, and effective communication skills.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. Educational flashmobs are pre-planned learning activities in which a large group of students perform pre-planned learning activities. A flash mob is a type of smart mob. Gathering of flashmob participants is carried out using electronic means of communication. So how can it be used in education? A flashmob is a mob that has activity, autonomous behavior, can make decisions according to a certain set of rules, interact with the environment, and also change independently. In doing so, the modeling system maintains at least one list of simulation events. In simulations based on one-way fast events, there is only one current event. However, multi-threaded simulation systems and simulation systems that support interval events may have the ability to handle multiple real-time issues. In both cases, there are serious problems with synchronization between existing events. It is known that intelligent education in higher education institutions is a holistic system - which manifests itself in interaction with the environment, immediate response to the system or process,

changes in the external environment; adapting to changing conditions; self-development and self-management; it is distinguished by such characteristics as effective achievement of the result. Interestingly, there are several logical chains of using new smart technologies: Changes in technological orders (fourth, fifth and sixth, etc.) SMART - smart education using artificial intelligence prevails; Technological change from WEB 2.0 to WEB 3.0 to cloud technologies in research related to electronic and distance education; intellectual generation, i.e. "X - Y - Z", the next generation (Z generation) considers the use of smart technologies and the use of information and communication tools as a matter of course, and recognizes that it is one of the necessary methods in the educational process. receivers . Therefore, the use of flash mobs as an intellectual environment is reflected in educational institutions and teachers' structure, infrastructure. Pedagogical aspects of the use of social media in higher education are subject to certain educational principles and are distinguished by their unique characteristics in teaching English. In the process of mastering the English learning material, it is inevitable that visual aids, drawings, written works, and completed exercises will be expressed in the context of digital technologies. In this case, the student's creativity, ingenuity, perception, and scope of thinking are determined by the extent to which he has mastered digital technologies and thus his motivation to learn English quickly. When teaching English to students on the basis of flash mobs, the connections between the methods of teaching, teaching, and the organization of the lesson and their chances of achieving the set goal are much higher, which include several integrates active methods and serves to implement educational goals step by step in classroom and non-auditory processes.

It is known that different forms and methods of innovative education are used in teaching English in higher education: educational technologies, information and communication technologies, programmed technologies, etc. In our opinion, lecture-visualization, creating a list of literature on the topic, enriching the studied English text with tables, schemes, preparing abstracts, diagrams, among the technologies of systematization and demonstration of knowledge in the rapid teaching of the English language, work with drawings, technological maps, systematization of literature on the topic, programmable survey with a structured answer. In the content of higher education, the selected educational material from English increases the productivity and effectiveness of teaching in the classroom and outside the classroom. When choosing teaching methods, it is appropriate for the teacher to choose the most convenient method aimed at effectively solving educational tasks, spending the least amount of time in the specific conditions of education. When perceiving the learning material in English, the student adopts the algorithm of the text structure as the main guide to understanding the content of the material. For example, test control is widely used to assess students' knowledge of English. If students are addressed with the help of digital technologies, for example, with tests based on cloud technology, this situation arouses great interest in students and provides an opportunity to determine the acquired competences related to science, along with the level of formation of the general worldview of students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS. Today, digital technologies are being used at all levels of education, starting from preschools. However, we have seen that these activities are not organized and did not always follow didactic principles. For example, homework is not just a boring "obligatory" task, but an interesting stage to move on to a new pursuit. The use of quests in the educational process, not just downloading educational material from the

platform, but solving a situational task, a problem in the form of a puzzle, arouses more interest in students, web quests that attract knowledge significantly increase their level of knowledge.

The “flash mob” is a 21st-century, technology-driven phenomenon. A flash mob is a group of people, usually unknown to each other, who assemble suddenly in a public place, perform some unusual or notable activity according to predetermined instructions, and then quickly disperse. Flash mob instructions are usually distributed via digital communication networks, such as an Internet posting, e-mail, or cell phones. In one example of a flash mob, “mobbers” gathered around a particular rug at Macy's department store in New York, saying that they were shopping for a “love rug” for their commune. In another, mobbers brought umbrellas and walked two city blocks singing songs from the movie *Mary Poppins*.

In the classroom, examples of flash mobs can be used to demonstrate a wide range of social influence concepts, such as authority, compliance, conformity, and group norms. Rather than simply reading and talking about flash mobs, however, I suggest that the best use of this concept is to create a flash mob, with the students as mobbers. In this paper, I will describe how I have incorporated a flash mob activity in my social psychology classes, and how I guide students in relating their behavior to different concepts. Finally, I present student feedback from two flash mob activities

PREPARING THE ACTIVITY. The guidelines for true flash mob activities are simple: the behavior must be silly, harmless, and peaceful, and should be short in duration (about 5 minutes). One behavior that I employ is walking around a public fountain, flapping and clucking like a chicken. Another is singing a popular song while walking in a circle in a public park. Other no-equipment behaviors include sitting on a wall making bird calls, applauding in a synchronized pattern, and forming a conga line.

Some flash mobs incorporate the use of cell phones, books, or newspapers in their activity. For example, one flash mob activity consisted of walking on a particular stretch of public sidewalk, taking out a cell phone, and yelling, “Yes, yes!”. In another flash mob, mobbers each brought a book and swapped with fellow mobbers for 10 minutes. A flash mob activity in Austin included slow-motion sword fighting with rolled-up newspapers.

Some flash mobs, such as the Macy's rug mob, have interfered with businesses; others, such as pillow-fight flash mobs (pillowfightclub.org, 2006), include a level of violence that goes beyond the purpose of the flash mob. In both of these cases, the ethics of the behavior are in question. To determine an ethical flash mob activity, and one that is in keeping with the spirit of flash mobs, consider some of the general rules of a “good flash mob,” as described by Johnson: Avoid places of business; don't get political; do not disrupt traffic; surprise the public, don't alarm them; and keep your shirt on.

Beyond the ethics of the flash mob, it is also important to consider the ethics for any classroom activity. Svinicki describes six principles of ethics for professors: autonomy, nonmaleficence, beneficence, justice, fidelity, and acting consciously. For the flash mob activity, the question of autonomy is of particular importance. Ethically, it is vital that students feel free to decline participation; additionally, as the students will discover in the post-activity discussion, the perception of autonomy has a significant influence on some social influence phenomena.

The location of a flash mob activity should be carefully considered. Nonmaleficence is important to consider; flash mobs should not impact others, such as business owners or the public, in a negative way. Therefore, no place of business should be considered for a flash mob. Instead, public areas, such as parks, sidewalks, or common areas, would be appropriate. I typically use a public fountain near our campus or a common area on campus.

The instructions that are communicated to the students should include a very specific time in which to begin and end the activity; synchronizing watches is advisable. It should also be clear that students can participate in or observe the activity, or not participate at all, with no negative consequences, and that the professor will not be participating. Students should approach the location of the activity separately, and disperse in different directions at the conclusion of the activity.

There are many ways in which instructions can be communicated to the students. In the flash mob activities that I have used, I tell the students about the day, time, place, and behavior during the two class sessions prior to the activity. Alternatively, instructions can be shared electronically, as information about a true flash mob would be. For example, professors who use an online source, such as WEBCT or Blackboard, can post instructions. Using e-mail is an option for some professors.

PERFORMING THE ACTIVITY. The flash mobs that I have organized were either at a nearby public fountain (a popular picnic spot) or on campus. I arranged the activity to begin 15 minutes after the scheduled class time, which allowed sufficient time for participants to walk to the location.

During the activity, the students should be completely autonomous. The professor should be an observer and should not give any guidance, especially regarding when to begin or end the activity. I typically have a location where I can watch the activity but not be seen by the participants.

The activity usually lasts between 2 and 5 minutes. At the conclusion of the activity, students converge back in the classroom for a post-activity discussion. I begin the discussion 15 minutes after the conclusion of the activity.

Students typically report feeling high levels of anxiety while they were waiting to begin. They attributed their anxiety to the expectation of being perceived as deviant, and the fear that they may experience rejection from society; they understand how painful social ostracism can be. Their discomfort can be discussed as it relates to the research by Williams and colleagues, which reveals that ostracism is psychologically and physically painful. For example, in the Eisenberger et study, participants played a game of computerized keep-away. When they were excluded from the game, their social pain was comparable to physical pain, as measured by an fMRI. After participating in a flash mob or not participating, because of high levels of anxiety students better understand some of the negative consequences of social ostracism.

Some students are surprised that they felt anxiety at the possibility that they would be ostracized by strangers (e.g., observers of the flash mob); it is easy for them to recognize that ostracism from their peer groups is unpleasant, but they do not realize the power of the threat of ostracism by society in general. Their experience is consistent with the Zadro study. In this study, participants again played the computerized keep-away game, but were given different information about their opponents. Even when participants were told that they were playing against a pre-programmed computer, they reported feeling the pain of ostracism.

After participating in the activity, norms were easily described. Some of the students discussed the norms of the location, such as, “People sit and eat lunch” and “You’re not supposed to look at anyone else.” Others pointed out the norms of the group: “You’re supposed to cluck,” “Most of us were flapping our arms.”

By pointing out these specific, conflicting norms, students gain an understanding of Cialdini’s focus theory of norms. According to Cialdini, norms fall into two categories: descriptive, or what is being done, and injunctive, or what should be done. Whether the norms influence an individual’s behavior depends

—at least in part

—on the situation, including the salience of the norms.

In the flash mob, norms of both the public and the mobbers were made salient, and the students were aware of these conflicting norms.

Did you participate in the activity? Why?

Students who did participate in the activity most often respond to this question with some form of “I did it because everyone else was doing it!” Clearly, conformity is one of the most salient concepts in the flash mob activity. Conformity refers to the way people change their behaviors (or attitudes, or beliefs) in order to fit in with others. Conformity can be discussed within the context of informational and normative social influence or in terms of public compliance and private acceptance.

Normative social influence occurs when people look to others to determine what social behavior is appropriate in a given situation. The classic example of normative social influence is Asch’s line study (although information influence was also present as described). In this study, participants were asked to indicate which of three lines matched a target line. When confederates gave obviously incorrect answers, many participants went along with the wrong answer, apparently in order to get along with the group. Students who participated in the flash mob are likely to have experienced public compliance and not private acceptance. They changed their behavior to go along with the group, even though it is unlikely that they would perform the behavior on their own. This type of conformity is akin to the public compliance. In comparison, most students agree that they will not perform the flash mob behavior on their own in the future. In other words, they have not experienced private acceptance: although they changed their behavior for the activity, they have not changed their beliefs about the behavior.

Was it easy to perform the behavior?

Most students report that starting the behavior was difficult, but it was very easy once everyone was participating. This response can lead to a discussion on crowd behavior and deindividuation. The emergent norm perspective of crowd behavior proposes that a group forms its own norms that the members. In comparison, deindividuation occurs when people in a group experience a decreased sense of individuality and self-awareness, and are no longer controlled by societal norms. Students can hypothesize which of these two theories better exemplifies their experience in the flash mob.

Would participating in the flash mob be different if the professor was present?

Students occasionally comment that the activity “would have been better” if I had told them when to begin the activity and when to end it. Students recognize that if I had told them that the activity was required, or if I had told them when to begin and end the behavior, they

would have felt much less anxiety; it would be easy to attribute their behavior to an authority figure. This suggestion relates directly to a discussion of obedience: performing an activity as a result of a command from an authority figure. Milgram performed a series of studies in which a participant was commanded to administer electric shocks to a confederate. He found that obedience was inversely related to the proximity of the authority figure. When the experimenter was a few feet away from the participant, obedience was surprisingly high; however, when the authority figure gave orders via telephone or via tape recording, participants were much less likely to obey commands to shock the confederate.

How might you increase the likelihood that observers would participate?

Students often have interesting ideas regarding this question. For example, one student proposed that the behavior should be singing a song that everyone knows; another proposed that the behavior should continue longer. This raised the topic of minority influence. It is possible for one dissenter to change the behavior of many within a group. To be effective, the dissenter needs to be consistent and confident. While the flash mob is not an individual, it is possible that the participants might inspire observers to join the group—if the group members are consistent and confident.

Was this activity worthwhile, even though you may have felt uncomfortable?

In post-activity discussions, students often report having felt high anxiety and embarrassment. In post-activity questionnaires, students rate this activity as worthwhile, useful, and enjoyable, and should be repeated in future classes (see Assessment, below). It is possible that the value of the activity outweighs the anxiety and embarrassment the students experienced; it is also possible that the students experience cognitive dissonance when asked to evaluate the activity. Cognitive dissonance occurs when a person experiences inconsistency between an attitude and a behavior. Some of the factors that increase the likelihood of cognitive dissonance include: the person must perceive that the behavior was a choice, the behavior was effortful, and the behavior had foreseeable, negative consequences. Therefore, students who participate in the flash mob are more likely to experience cognitive dissonance if their participation was completely voluntary, their embarrassment or anxiety was high, and they knew beforehand that they were going to be embarrassed or anxious. If they experienced cognitive dissonance, their ratings of the activity should be high.

What are some of the ethical concerns for this activity?

Students are quick to point out some of the ethical concerns in flash mobs as mentioned earlier (e.g., interfering with businesses, keeping participation optional). This question is a natural segue to a discussion of the American Psychological Association (APA) ethical guidelines. These guidelines are in place to direct the ethics of all psychologists, whether they are working in a classroom, in a laboratory, or in a clinic. There are five general principles: “Beneficence and Nonmaleficence,” “Fidelity and Responsibility,” “Integrity,” “Justice,” and “Respect for People’s Rights and Dignity”. Students can appreciate how each of these principles influences their participation in the flash mob

FLASH MOBS VS NORM-BREAKING ACTIVITIES

Professors of social psychology often include an activity wherein students break or imagine breaking a social norm. The flash mob is similar in that it includes a norm-breaking component; however, the flash mob activity improves on the typical norm-breaking activity because it incorporates so many social influence concepts. For example, the flash mob

includes group dynamics, which can be used to demonstrate deindividuation, affiliation motivation, and the power of the in-group. The flash mob has the added attraction of being technologically driven and contemporary, which brings social influence principles into the student's world. Finally, because the class participates (or observes) as a group, the activity serves as a bond among the students, which contributes to group cohesiveness.

Conclusion: Teaching Flash Mobs represent a novel and engaging method for English language acquisition, integrating spontaneity, linguistic diversity, cultural understanding, and technological elements. By fostering interactive learning experiences and creating a sense of community, this approach adds a dynamic dimension to language education. As educators continue to explore innovative methods to inspire and empower students, Teaching Flash Mobs emerge as a vibrant tool for enhancing language proficiency and communication skills in a real-world context. Flash mobs are intriguing social phenomena. Organizers create a social group out of strangers, and the mobbers are both group members and deviants at the same time. These overlapping roles afford opportunities to discuss many terms and concepts that are relevant to social influence, including one of the most important: across time, across cultures, and across nations, humans are social beings.

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